

ONLINE RECRUITMENT APPLICATION AS SOLUTION PROPOSAL DURING THE CORONA PANDEMIC

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Abstract

Since the Corona pandemic has altered employment trends and brought about significant changes in the job search industry, it presents certain difficulties for professionals looking for suitable employment. Therefore, if you're looking for work right now, you should stay up to date with changes to improve your chances of finding a position that's a good fit. The purpose of this paper is to investigate how the Corona pandemic has affected the rise in electronic recruitment. The report also offered a model for electronic recruitment applicants that can assist many job seekers and serve as a reference while doing a job search online.

Keywords: Job, E-Recruitment, Corona virus, Pandemic, Unemployment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many people's lives have been completely upended by the developing corona virus problem, whether they are employed full-time or part-time, wealthy or impoverished, in the tourism, restaurant, or aviation industries, or any other industry. Millions of individuals around the world either don't have jobs or won't have jobs in 2021. People who have lost their jobs experience significant dread for the future, feelings of despair, and perhaps feelings of guilt and even denigration.

This year, according to the International Monetary Fund, there will be a 4.9 percent recession, with "low-income families and unskilled workers" suffering the hardest. Today, this approach has been tried, tested, and proven; more significantly, it cannot be replaced. Professional recruiters and employers alike rely on job portals as a significant supply of professional skills, sometimes in addition to more conventional methods of recruitment. Thanks to the value, functionality, and usability of contemporary online job sites, there has been a paradigm shift in how businesses hire. This is due to the rapid increase in Internet access levels, the blending of geographical borders when it comes to professional mobility, and the frantic pursuit of better skills in the booming regional economies. There is no doubt that this medium will remain.

2. E- RECRUITMENT CONCEPT:

The electronic recruitment system is a website that attracts foreign talent to fill openings in various types of organizations. Visitors and job seekers can use the site to search for openings, apply for openings, suggest openings to friends or coworkers who might be qualified for the position, follow up on the application status, communicate directly with hiring managers,

follow up on interview details, withdraw from a job application, and other services related to employment.

3. HOW TO USE E-RECRUITING

A smart e-recruitment system relies on systems that are strengthened by artificial intelligence-related characteristics. It concentrates on different departments and chooses the best candidates without the need for human intervention, which helps to increase transparency and reliability and opens up opportunities for interaction in smart employment. The system is based on a record of recruitment and research conducted by it, and builds trends through searches that choose the most suitable job elements. It uses a variety of technologies that use artificial intelligence in the smart electronic recruitment system to select the most suitable employees.

4. E-RECRUITMENT ADVANTAGES

A. Cutting the hiring process time

The employment search and application procedure can continue 24 hours a day, seven days a week, thanks to e-recruitment. On a job board like Bayt.com, employers may post a job in as little as 20 minutes with no size restrictions and begin getting resumes right away. As soon as job seekers locate the ad, it continues to be effective for 30 days, during which time resumes are still being received.

This is in contrast to conventional techniques, which require the employee to wait until the end of the month to benefit from an advertisement that appears in the newspaper after a week and for only one day or in a publication for a particular geographically specified area. Electronic hiring typically accelerates the hiring cycle at every stage, from posting to getting CVs to filtering to managing communications and workflow, by 70% compared to traditional hiring methods.

B. Reduced hiring expenses

When compared to the cost of using search engines and/or conventional advertising media, the cost of posting positions and/or looking for the right candidates on job portals can be 90% lower. A job posting on Bayt.com, which costs \$250, is significantly more affordable and cost-effective than paying 30% of what many traditional hiring firms charge annually or spending the same amount to promote in newspapers or other publications and grew.

C. Broader Range of Business

Electronic employment portals have a current and model database of skills that includes all job cadres and professions in all regions, in contrast to traditional means of employment that are restricted to the professional level, geographic dimension, profession, and other criteria. To ensure diversity, frequent updating, and high-quality databases, a lot of money is spent. The dependencies that keep the job portals prominent, full of the appropriate individuals for the right jobs, and often frequented by the right job searchers are likewise kept stable by deployed business development teams.

D. A sizable number of job seekers

Employment searchers profit from the variety of options offered by internet job portals. With a single mouse click, they can apply for jobs in organizations, fields of work, and locations that they otherwise would not be familiar with. Companies and recruiters will be able to contact job seekers immediately about unannounced positions if they post their CVs online.

E. Creates a pathway for secrecy

Both the recruiter and the job seeker can maintain their anonymity during the hiring process. If a position is sensitive in nature, employers can look for CVs without making the position public or they can promote the position anonymously. Additionally, job seekers can post their resumes online while maintaining the privacy of their names and workplaces.

F. Creates space for initiative

In the case of electronic recruitment, the head of company or the hiring official has complete control over the hiring process and is able to speak with potential employees directly. The people with the necessary qualities can be found, filtered, assessed, and chosen directly through this method without the aid of an intermediary. The fact that the boss or recruiter is the only one in charge of the hiring process endows him with knowledge about the market's dynamics and the level of competition for the post. Additionally, he can ensure that the person hired will be the best fit long term.

G. Creating a database of references

The most appealing and notable resumes from previous searches can be saved by recruiters in order to create a pre-screened biographies priority database of high-skill candidates.

5. RECRUITMENT AND COVID 19

The coronavirus pandemic presented certain difficulties for professionals looking for suitable employment because it altered employment trends and underwent significant changes in the job search industry. The recent Coronavirus epidemic had a major effect on both the domestic and international labor markets. In the second quarter of 2020, working hours fell by 14%, which is the same as losing 400 million full-time jobs. 6.1 billion Individuals work in the informal sector, and underrepresented groups like young people, women, and persons with special needs are among those most impacted by the labor market.

We are aware that the correct classification supports the development of regulations and policies to reduce social protection gaps, as well as to reduce the exploitation of workers and unfair support from employers, and that the classification of employment status of workers has a significant impact on their strength and their ability to reach appropriate social protection in light of the change in work patterns associated with digital transformation. Effective monitoring is crucial, and this entails gathering information and creating reports on how social protection systems have been modified to take into account evolving employment patterns. We will endeavor to uphold workers' rights and establish social protection systems that are robust and flexible enough to offer sufficient help for everyone.

6. ONLINE RECRUITMENT FOR APPLICANT PROPOSED

A. Be well-prepared to look for work

Because of the widespread Coronavirus, our current situation may provide you with the opportunity to find the extra time you needed to update and strengthen your CV. Give a CV, which is a ticket to the job market, a lot of consideration. You can update and improve your CV or even generate a new resume if you so choose. We advise writing a unique cover letter or allocating an appropriate CV to each job you wish to apply for if you wish to do so.

B. Study the labor market thoroughly now

Keep in mind that not all industries are impacted by the spread of the coronavirus in the same way. On the contrary, the virus has helped some industries, including those that provide food, medicine, medical supplies, delivery services, and other supplies, grow. Some industries have experienced long-term negative effects from the virus, while others have experienced temporary or short-term effects. As a result, although many businesses are cutting staff, others must hire new workers to keep up with the increasing demand for their products or services in these circumstances.

C. Concentrate on internet job hunting

We usually advise job seekers to use both conventional and unconventional job search strategies, but in certain situations, internet search should take center stage. Spend time researching employment websites like Akhtaboot and the websites and social media pages of the company you want to apply to. This is important because all businesses are now required to post job openings online.

D. Research the possibilities for working from home

As we previously indicated, not all industries are affected equally by the virus because many of them allow employees to work remotely, such as firms that offer technology solutions or consultancies. Therefore, we advise that you concentrate on these businesses as well, as they can still be hiring and attracting people, during the search process.

E. Prepare for video interviews by practicing

Companies that are actively hiring will undoubtedly use video interviews. So begin rehearsing for this kind of interview if you haven't already. Verify that your computer's camera and audio are functioning. Make sure the lighting and background where you sit are proper before any video interview, and dress appropriately as if you were going to a genuine job interview.

F. Develop your abilities

The majority of these projects are free, and job sites, training facilities, academic institutions, and universities are all presently focusing on offering online lectures, seminars, and training courses. As a result, the current time offers you the chance to improve your talents by using the content that is readily available online.

Figure (1): Proposed Online Procurement Solution

7. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

International businesses were not exempt from the Corona pandemic's mass layoffs of staff, which raises numerous concerns among technology specialists about the shift in supply and demand in a sector that is seeing a surge in various regions.

The purpose of this paper is to illustrate the idea of electronic recruitment and its advantages for both businesses and job seekers, while there are also some disadvantages. Therefore, the benefits of online hiring are: reduced expenses for the organization, Additionally, posting jobs online is less expensive than placing ads in newspapers, there are no middlemen, recruitment time is reduced (by more than 65%), e-recruitment makes it easier to find candidates with the necessary skills, improves the effectiveness of the hiring process, and provides applicants and employers with access to a variety of online resumes 24 hours a day, seven days a week. Additionally, online recruitment aids employers in weeding out unqualified candidates.

Despite the many positives, it is clear that e-recruitment also has significant drawbacks. A few of these are as follows:

- A. Millions of resumes must be screened and their reliability and drawing abilities verified, which a difficult and time-consuming process for businesses is.
- B. In many places, for instance India, there is little internet use, little access to the internet, and little awareness.
- C. Employers cannot just rely on online hiring practices.

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